

Research article

Misbehavior detection in intelligent transportation systems based on federated learning

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ABSTRACT

Misbehavior detection represents a key security approach in vehicular scenarios to identify attacks that cannot be detected by traditional cryptographic mechanisms. In this context, the application of Machine Learning (ML) techniques has been widely considered to identify increasingly sophisticated misbehavior attacks. However, most of the proposed approaches are based on centralized settings, which could pose privacy issues, as well as an increased latency leading to severe consequences in the vehicular environment where real-time and scalability requirements are challenging. To address this issue, we propose a collaborative learning approach based on Federated Learning (FL) for vehicles' misbehavior detection. We use the reference misbehavior dataset VeReMi, which is re-balanced by applying the SMOTE-Tomek technique. We carry out a thorough evaluation considering different balancing settings and number of nodes. The evaluation results overcome recent state-of-the-art approaches, with an overall accuracy of 93% using an optimized multilayer perceptron (MLP) for multiclass classification.

1. Introduction

In an increasingly hyperconnected vehicular ecosystem, the sharing of information generated by vehicles and roadside infrastructure is key for more effective and efficient management of traffic conditions [1]. Indeed, the strong development of electronic components and external interfaces of current vehicles has enabled an increase in the communication through V2V (vehicle-to-vehicle) and V2I (vehicle-to-infrastructure) communications as a basis for the future autonomous vehicles. Specifically, vehicles use the well-known Basic Safety Messages (BSM) according to Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE) standards, or Cooperative Awareness Message (CAM) and Decentralized Environmental Notification Message (DENM) messages according to European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) standards [2] containing information to avoid accidents or warnings to drivers. To protect these messages, the use of a Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) in which vehicles are equipped with the cryptographic material required to encrypt and sign messages is widely considered. Despite the deployment of cryptographic approaches, vehicles could still forge information such as speed or position coordinates, while using the correct cryptographic material to protect it [3]. This aspect could have severe consequences ultimately affecting passengers' safety. Therefore, the use of cryptography must be complemented with additional techniques that enable the identification of misbehaving vehicles.

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Although *misbehavior detection* has attracted significant interest in recent years, most of the proposed approaches use centralized Machine Learning (ML), applied to huge amounts of data from different vehicles [3]. These centralized systems raise significant privacy concerns, as the aggregation of data from numerous vehicles can potentially be linked to specific drivers and passengers, allowing for the inference of sensitive information. Furthermore, the use of centralized ML approaches is associated with high latency [4], which is a crucial aspect for misbehavior detection due to scalability and real-time requirements [5]. It could be exacerbated in the vehicular context where vehicles continually generate huge amounts of data. In light of these limitations of traditional centralized ML systems, the shift towards Federated Learning (FL) [6], has emerged as a collaborative learning approach where parties do not need to share their data. Instead, each node trains on its local data to update a global model that is aggregated by a central server at each training round using an aggregation function. This method not only mitigates privacy and latency issues but also aligns with the real-time and scalable requirements essential for effective misbehavior detection in vehicular contexts. While the use of FL is proposed for a plethora of vehicular applications [5,7], only a recent paper [8] proposes a FL approach for misbehavior detection, although it does not offer an exhaustive evaluation or details about the ML model being employed.

In this direction, our work proposes a FL-enabled misbehavior detection approach using the VeReMi dataset [9], which has been widely used in other works [10–12]. It includes position spoofing attacks, which can pose serious safety risks in the vehicular ecosystem [13]. A close approach to our work is proposed by [8], where a simple Neural Network (NN) is employed. However, their work does not implement a real scenario in which each node maintains its own dataset private, but they artificially divide the dataset into 10 clients. On the contrary, we partition the VeReMi dataset based on the vehicle's ID, so that each vehicle actually operates as an FL client. This approach represents a more realistic scenario where each vehicle is able to train the model by using its local dataset. Furthermore, we carry out a re-balancing process of the dataset by using the SMOTE-Tomek technique [14], which combines undersampling and oversampling to evaluate its impact on the FL setting. As ML model, we use an optimized multilayer perceptron (MLP), which is evaluated according to different aggregation functions, including the recently proposed Fed+ [15]. In addition, we select a subset of nodes from the VeReMi dataset to achieve a trade-off between accuracy and the delay required for the training process. Our implementation uses the Flower framework [16], and we employ the Matthew Correlation Coefficient (MCC) and the Cohen Kappa Score (CKS) metrics to obtain a more reliable view of the model's performance under different balancing conditions in the dataset. Therefore, our contributions are:

- Design and implementation of a FL architecture based on an optimized MLP for the collaborative misbehavior detection in vehicular scenarios.
- Re-balancing of the VeReMi dataset using SMOTE-Tomek that is made publicly available.
- Evaluation of the proposed FL approach for multiclass classification considering different aggregation functions (FedAvg [6] and Fed+ [15]).
- Selection of clients from the VeReMi dataset to analyze the balance between the performance of the federated model and the delay required for training.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 analyzes the current state of the art. Then, Section 3 provides an overview of the system model for the proposed FL-enabled misbehavior detection approach. The main aspects of our proposal, including the dataset, re-balancing process and training algorithm are described in Section 4. Then, Section 5 describes the evaluation results of our solution, and Section 6 concludes the paper.

2. Related work

The development of misbehavior detection strategies for the vehicular ecosystem has attracted an increasing interest last years, especially because of potential safety implications for drivers and passengers [3]. According to our analysis, most of the recent approaches are based on the use of ML techniques and the VeReMi dataset, which is considered as the reference dataset for position spoofing attacks in vehicular environments [9]. In this paragraph, we describe some recent works considering centralized settings based on different ML models for misbehavior detection using this dataset. In particular, [17] integrates the use of plausibility checks with k-nearest neighbors (K-NN) and support vector machine (SVM) to build a multiclass classifier to detect the attacks considered in the VeReMi dataset. Furthermore, authors create an updated version of this dataset by adding the sender and receiver fields of the messages contained in the dataset. Also using plausibility checks, [10] extends the evaluation of the previous work by considering additional supervised ML techniques, such as Random Forest (RF) and Naïve Bayes (NB). Another multiclass classifier is proposed by [18] to identify VeReMi attacks as well as false alert attacks by comparing different ML models. This work was extended by [19], which integrates a reputation mechanism based on Dempster–Shafer theory [20]. RF and KNN are also used by [21] for misbehavior detection using the VeReMi dataset. In this case, the authors consider additional features, such as the angle of arrival based on the distance between sender and receiver, and considering the RSSI values of the dataset. An extended version of this work is described in [11], which provides a comprehensive evaluation of different ML techniques for each attack on the dataset. Furthermore, [12] proposes an RF-based multi-class classification approach, whose accuracy is compared to other ML techniques. In a similar direction, [13,22] compare the performance of several supervised ML techniques for each type of attack on the Veremi dataset. The use of a Broad Learning System (BLS) [23] is considered by [4] as an incremental learning approach to adapt the model considering new data, which is continuously generated. Furthermore, the authors compare this approach with traditional ML classifiers on three different datasets, including VeReMi. Moreover, [24] proposes an edge architecture in which a long short-term memory (LSTM) based unsupervised ML approach is built and evaluated on the same dataset.

While the previous approaches provide different insights on the use of ML techniques for misbehavior detection considering the VeReMi dataset, these works are based on the use of centralized ML approaches in which a central entity needs to obtain vehicles' data. Even if vehicles need to share periodically BSM (or CAM/DENM messages), the use of ML techniques over all the data generated by vehicles (e.g., GPS data) for misbehavior detection could lead to privacy concerns. To mitigate such issues, the application of FL in the automotive sector has gained significant momentum in recent years and various studies have explored the advantages of FL for a variety of ITS applications. Therefore, we focus in existing FL-based approaches for vehicular environments. In particular, a general overview of FL for Vehicular Internet of Things (VIoT) was presented in [5], where different FL approaches are evaluated and considered in the VIoT context. Authors also identify several advantages from the use of FL in this scenario, such as low communication overhead, efficiency and the possibility to involve data from more vehicles compared to traditional centralized approaches. General aspects on the application of FL to the vehicular domain were also discussed in [7], which presents the concept of Federated Vehicular Network (FVN) based on a collaborative learning process of vehicles and infrastructure with powerful computing capabilities. The proposed approach also includes the use of blockchain to mitigate the potential malicious behavior of the entities participating in the training process. Furthermore, [25] describes the main advantages of FL around the scenarios related to traffic management and autonomous driving.

Despite the advantages derived from the use of FL in the vehicular environment [26], only a recent work proposed an FL-based misbehavior detection approach considering the VeReMi dataset. Specifically, [8] proposes a system where vehicles locally train a neural network using their data to collaboratively build a global model for misbehavior detection. However, the authors do not provide details related to the neural network being used and they do not describe how the dataset is distributed among the different vehicles. Unlike this work, we split VeReMi according to each vehicle considered in the dataset and use SMOTE-Tomek [14] to locally balance the dataset portion of each client. We design an MLP-based FL process and select a subset of the dataset's clients to further improve the model's performance. Furthermore, it should be noted that some of the aforementioned works describe challenges related to the application of FL in the vehicular ecosystem [5,7]; while they are not directly addressed in this work, the aspects related to mobility and scalability, as well as their impact on the FL process represent part of our future work in this area.

3. System model

The overall system model of our FL-enabled misbehavior detection approach is pictorially described in Fig. 3 where the main components are identified. The *Vehicular ITS stations* represent modern vehicles and/or future automated vehicles, which are equipped with ML/DL local computing platforms. They exchange messages among themselves and with the road infrastructure either using CAM/DENM messages (on the basis of ETSI standards) or BSM messages (on the basis of SAE standards). The ML/DL local component in each ITS station trains a local ML model on its data and the messages received by other ITS stations to update the global model shared by the Cloud FL node in each training round. Furthermore, after a certain number of rounds, each ITS station can use such model for misbehavior detection by using new data obtained from its sensors and other vehicles. In case of detecting a misbehavior, they can communicate such information to the Cloud FL node, which will store the new data in the *misbehavior information* database.

For the communication with the Cloud FL node, ITS stations' messages go through the *roadside infrastructure*. The network is composed by both *fixed* and *wireless* links. In the case of the wireless links, which are used between ITS stations and roadside units, they can be based on the Dedicated Short Range Communications (DSRC) at 5.9 GHz or cellular links. Wireless links are used for the communication among vehicles (V2V) and from vehicle to infrastructure (V2I) while the communication between the road ITS stations and the cloud is mostly fixed. In the case of DSRC links, there may be the need to change the standard specification to support the transport of the information generated by ITS stations, while the current 4G cellular networks are able to carry such information without changes to the standards specifications. Then, the *Cloud FL* component implements an aggregation method (e.g., FedAvg or Fed+, as described in Section 4.4) to aggregate the local results from the ITS stations. The resulting aggregated model is sent again to the ITS stations to be updated through a new training round.

Furthermore, the Cloud FL could also be enabled to receive data from the ITS stations concerning to certain misbehaving vehicles to be stored in the database. The information contained in this database could be used as an input to other systems that could establish appropriate countermeasures against misbehaving vehicles, for example, by revoking its cryptographic credentials to limit their communication. Indeed, while it is not the focus of our work, the system model assumes the use of a PKI developed for Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems (C-ITS) [27] to provide basic security properties, including authentication and integrity. In particular, the use of Enrollment Certificates (EC) for authentication, and short-lived anonymized certificates for V2X communications, named Authorization Tickets (AT) or pseudonym certificates could be considered based on ETSI standards [28]. ATs are defined for the DSRC messages (e.g. CAM). Then, the amount of information that can be transmitted would be limited to few hundreds of bytes. This limit would be suitable for the transmission of the local ML/DL model updates mostly consisting of weights and values of hyperparameters in the ML/DL algorithms in our federated scenario. As an alternative, integrity and confidentiality at the application layer for the communication of summary local data (e.g., based on cellular networks) could be based or derived from ECs, which are supposed to be active for a number of years (see Fig. 1).

Based on the previous description, in this system model, ITS stations (i.e. vehicles) act as FL clients performing local training by using the VeReMi dataset [9] (see Section 4.1) and the global model, which is shared by the Cloud FL in each training round. In our case, as described in Section 4.3, we use an optimized MLP for the local training. Then, the updated weights, as well as misbehavior data derived from the ITS stations are sent to the Cloud FL node, which uses an aggregation method to combine the local weights. As described in Section 4.4, we compare the performance of the well-known FedAvg method [6], with the recent Fed+ approach [15].

Fig. 1. Pictorial description of the system model.

The rationale behind choosing FedAvg and Fed+ for our study is guided by two principal factors. Firstly, FedAvg is recognized as the predominant aggregation function, so it serves as our baseline. Secondly, we adopt Fed+ given its enhanced performance in non-iid scenarios, like the one considered in this work. This makes it a promising approach for FL aggregation specially in the case of unbalanced datasets as we have previously demonstrated [29].

4. FL-enabled misbehavior detection for C-ITS

This section describes the dataset, balancing process, as well as the ML model and the aggregation methods being considered in our work. Based on these components, we also provide a description of the resulting FL-enabled misbehavior detection approach.

4.1. Dataset

For the implementation of our approach, we use the version of the VeReMi dataset provided by [17]. The dataset was built through 225 simulations and the VEINS simulator considering 5 position forging attacks, 3 vehicle densities (low, medium and high), 3 attacker densities (10, 20 and 30 percent), and each parameter set was repeated 5 times for randomization. VeReMi is a labeled dataset that contains the message logs of the attacking and benign vehicles, which includes reception time stamp, claimed transmission time, claimed sender, unique message ID, GPS position (x, y, z), RSSI value, position noise and speed noise vector for each receiving vehicle in every scenario. Furthermore, each simulation is represented by two types of files: ground truth files and log files.

The ground truth file includes the values of the BSM attributes and assigns an attacker type to each vehicle considering that legitimate vehicles are represented by class 0, i.e., the benign samples are represented by class 0. The attacks included, which correspond to the different classes of the Veremi dataset, are: (1) *Constant*: vehicle transmits a fixed position; (2) *Constant Offset*: offset added to vehicle's actual position; (3) *Random*: vehicle transmits random position from simulation area; (4) *Random Offset*: random position from preconfigured rectangular area around the vehicle; and (5) *Eventual Stop*: attacker behaves normally for some time and then transmits current position. Moreover, each vehicle also has an associated log file that includes all the received BSM messages from neighboring vehicles in a range of 300 m. The content of such BSM messages could include forged data representing the information provided by attacker vehicles.

4.2. Dataset preprocessing

In this phase, we split the dataset according to the number of vehicles, so that each vehicle is considered as a FL client. The VeReMi dataset has 2167944 samples, of which 1601146 represent benign data and 566798 refer to attacks, of which the 5 attack classes have 122374, 112755, 110780, 110554, and 110081 samples respectively. Hence, the benign-attack traffic ratio of VeReMi is 76:24, and a similar proportion is also found in each vehicle's dataset. Therefore, individual cars have more benign traffic samples compared to attack classes, as well as an unbalanced number of samples regarding the attack type. Such aspect could lead to misleading results, as the model could not learn properly from the minority class. Indeed, it could be exacerbated when using datasets for intrusion detection where certain attacks are represented by a small number of samples. This situation is

inherent to FL settings where the use of non-iid data leads to imbalanced datasets among the different parties [29]. To address this issue, oversampling and undersampling techniques are usually employed to modify class distributions.

Indeed, a recent work [30] proposed P2PK-SMOTE as a modified version of the well-known oversampling technique SMOTE [31] in the context of FL-enabled intrusion detection. However, the use of an oversampling method could lead to overfitting issues, making it possible to create ambiguous examples if there is a strong overlap for the classes [32]. Based on this aspect, we use a combination of oversampling and undersampling techniques to rebalance the VeReMi dataset based on the SMOTE-Tomek method [14]. SMOTE creates new samples in the minority classes by making a linear combination between one point and its k -nearest neighbors with Eq. (1).

$$d_n = rn + (1 - r)d_o, \quad (1)$$

where d_n is the new data point generated, d_o is the original sample of a minority class, n is a neighbor of d_n , and r is a variable between 0 and 1 which creates intermediate points between d_o and n . Then, Tomek links removes those points of different classes that are close neighbors. In particular, it takes a couple of these near points (x_i, x_j) , one from the minority class and one from the majority class, and it removes the one of the majority class; therefore, the point of the majority class closest to the minority class is removed. After applying SMOTE-Tomek to the VeReMi dataset, the average length of each client increases from 4353 to 16 124. Additionally, we measure the skewness of the classes of each client using the Shannon entropy [33], which shifts from 0.55 to 0.98. However, the number of vehicles is reduced from 498 to 449 due to some clients have too few samples and SMOTE-Tomek cannot be applied. Hence, in Section 5 we use the clients in which SMOTE-Tomek can be applied. Furthermore, we also remove the features that cannot be used for ML (e.g., car ID) and normalize the data. It should be noted that although SMOTE-TOMEK has been applied in ML scenarios [32], this is the first work that evaluates the impact of this technique in the context of a FL setting. Furthermore, we make the balanced and divided version of the VeReMi dataset¹ publicly available, so that it can be used for other researchers in the future.

4.3. Federated MLP model

As a ML model, we use a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP), which is a widely used classifier in the form of neural network with more than one hidden layer. MLP is a feed-forward artificial neural network that consists of a number of neurons connected by linking weights. The structure of a MLP is characterized by having at least three layers: input and output layers and at least one or several hidden layers between them. Each neuron in every layer is connected to all the neurons of the next layer, thus making it a fully connected network. Each node, apart from the input nodes, has a nonlinear activation function. The process of MLP consists of the input layer receiving the input data from outside, then passing it to the first hidden layer, which will be forwarded until it finally reaches the output layer. In order to train the MLP, the backpropagation method is used [34]. In short, it is based on the chain rule, it takes the final weights and minimizes them in order to reduce the loss function. These weights are the result of the activation function of the prior layer. Then, it minimizes these weights using derivatives, and recursively, minimizing all of them.

In particular, we use an optimized MLP, whose parameters have been obtained through the GridSearchCV module.² It uses cross-validation through a grid search to get the combination of parameters reaching the highest accuracy. This optimization enables the model to prevent overfitting problems [35], since the model has the optimum number of layers and neurons. Furthermore, the application of SMOTE-Tomek contributes to mitigating overfitting by ensuring an equal number of samples for each class, thereby promoting a more balanced dataset. Based on this optimization, the MLP in each client consists of: (1) Input layer with 17 neurons; (2) A first hidden layer with 350 neurons and Relu activation function; (3) A second hidden layer with 50 neurons and Relu activation function; and (4) Output layer with 6 neurons and Sigmoid activation function. Furthermore, we chose Nadam as the optimizer with learning rate equal to 0.005. Fig. 2 provides an overview of such MLP. In this picture, $f_1(x) = f_2(x) = \max(0, x)$ are the Relu activation function, $f_3(x) = \frac{1}{1+e^{-x}}$ is the Sigmoid activation function, and W_{ij}^k are the weights of the layer k .

4.4. Aggregation algorithms

In a FL setting, aggregation algorithms are used by a server (or aggregator) to aggregate all the clients' weights in each training round. The most common aggregation function is a weighted average (FedAvg [6]). However, as we have researched in recent works [29], the performance of FedAvg may be degraded in non independent and identically distributed (non-iid) scenarios with highly skewed data. For this reason, we also consider Fed+ [15], a family of algorithms that were developed to handle non-iid data.

4.4.1. FedAvg

FedAvg is the simplest way of aggregating FL clients' weights. Let be $W_r^k = (w_i^k)_r$ the weights of client k at round r , and $W_r = (w_i)_r$ the weights of the global model at round r . So the new weights W_{r+1} will be:

$$W_{r+1} = \sum_k \frac{d_i}{D} W_r^k \quad (2)$$

where d_i is the total data of client k and D is the total data of all clients.

¹ https://github.com/Enrique-Marmol/Decentralized_Misbehavior_Detection_based_on_FL_for_Intelligent_Transportation_Systems.

² https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.model_selection.GridSearchCV.html.

Fig. 2. Pictorial description of the neural network.

4.4.2. Fed+

Fed+ (or Fedplus) is designed to handle non-iid data distributions, which are common in FL scenarios, where parties could have very different amounts of samples for each class. For this purpose, Fed+ is based on a robust, personalized approach to FL, in which parties are not forced to converge to a single central point.

In summary, in FedAvg the objective function is

$$\min F(W) = \frac{1}{D} \sum f_k(W^k) \text{ subject to } w_i = w_i^k, \tag{3}$$

where f_k is the loss function of the client k . In the case of Fed+, the idea is to add a penalty function to replace the hard condition of (3). Hence, the new equation will be:

$$\min F_\mu(W) = \frac{1}{D} \sum [f_k(W^k) + \mu B(W^k, A(W))], \tag{4}$$

where $\mu > 0$ is a penalty constant, A is an aggregation function of the clients' weights, and $B(\cdot, \cdot)$ is a distance function that penalizes the deviation of a local model W^k from the output of $A(\cdot)$.

A particular case is considered when $\mu = 0$, which represents the non-federated setting where every party is independent, namely, the distributed case. Moreover, if $\mu > 0$, $A = \frac{1}{D} \sum W^k$, and $B(W^k, \bar{W}) = \infty$ if $W^k \neq \bar{W}$, and 0 otherwise, it is Eq. (3) case.

Finally, applying this to the local weights, it leads to the formula

$$W^k \leftarrow \theta [W^k - \nu \nabla f_k(W^k)] + (1 - \theta) Z^k, \tag{5}$$

where ν is the learning rate, $\theta = \frac{1}{1+\nu\mu}$ is a constant between 0 and 1 that controls the degree of regularization, i.e., it is used to determine how much local weights are affected by the mean weights obtained through the federated training process, and Z^k is the result of $B(W^k, \bar{W})$.

4.5. Overall FL process

Based on the aspects described in this section, and the overall system model described in Section 3, our FL approach is reflected in Fig. 3. Firstly, each portion of the VeReMi dataset D_k of client k is balanced into \bar{D}_k through SMOTE-Tomek function F . The details of the SMOTE-Tomek function are provided in Algorithm 1. Then, each client trains its model with its own balanced data, using a certain number of epochs. As a result of this training process, they generate the weights W_k , which are sent to the server (i.e., the Cloud FL node of Section 3). The server aggregates the incoming weights W_k into W using an aggregation function G (i.e., FedAvg or Fed+) and sends the result back to the clients. Then, they train again their model using these weights W as initial weights of the MLP. This process between server and clients is repeated until a certain number of rounds is reached. In our case, we evaluate our approach considering 20 rounds and 5 epochs in each round, as described in Section 5. Furthermore, Algorithm 1 provides additional details about our proposed FL-enabled misbehavior detection approach considering Fed+ as aggregation function.

Fig. 3. Scheme of our federated environment. (1) Apply SMOTE-Tomek, (2) Train neural network, (3) Send weights to the server, (4) Aggregate received weights, and (5) Send aggregated weights to the clients.

5. Evaluation results

For the evaluation of our FL-enabled misbehavior detection approach, we considered several federated scenarios running in a virtual machine with processor Intel(R) Xeon(R) Silver 4214R CPU @ 2.40 GHz with 24 cores and 196 GB of RAM. Furthermore, we used Flower [16] as the federated learning framework. It provides an end-to-end implementation and the possibility to customize several aspects of the model for further evaluation. Furthermore, we employed TensorFlow,³ and Scikit-learn⁴ as Python libraries to obtain the results below by implementing the MLP previously described.

5.1. Evaluation metrics

Most of the works considering a FL setting use the well-known metrics to evaluate ML approaches, such as accuracy ($\frac{TP+TN}{TP+FP+FN+TN}$), recall ($\frac{TP}{TP+FN}$), precision ($\frac{TP}{TP+FP}$), and f1-score ($\frac{2*recall*precision}{recall+precision}$), where TP = true positive, TN = true negative, FP = false positive and FN = false negative. However, under different balancing conditions, these metrics do not provide a reliable picture about the performance of the model [36]. To address such issue, in this work, we consider the Matthew Correlation Coefficient and the Cohen Kappa Score, which have been considered in recent works [37].

5.1.1. Matthew correlation coefficient

Matthew Correlation Coefficient (MCC) is a metric that takes into account all four values in the confusion matrix (TP, TN, FP, FN):

$$MCC = \frac{TP \times TN - FN \times FP}{\sqrt{(TP + FP)(TP + FN)(TN + FP)(TN + FN)}} \quad (6)$$

MCC value is comprised between -1 and 1 . A value close to 1 means that both classes are predicted well, even if one class is disproportionately under- (or over-) represented. If $MCC = 1$ then $FP = FN = 0$ which means the model is perfect. When $MCC = -1$ then $TP = TN = 0$ which means a negative correlation, so the model gives the opposite true value. If $MCC = 0$, it means that the model is totally random.

For multiclass classification (which is our case), the formula is slightly modified. Let be C the confusion matrix, and K the number of classes:

$$MCC = \frac{c \times s - \sum_{k=1}^K p_k \times t_k}{\sqrt{(s^2 - \sum_{k=1}^K p_k^2)(s^2 - \sum_{k=1}^K t_k^2)}} \quad (7)$$

³ <https://www.tensorflow.org/>.

⁴ <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/>.

Algorithm 1 Algorithm of our federated learning framework**Input:** Number of rounds R , number of parties P , number of epochs E , dataset of party k D_k , and learning rate ν **Output:** Global model W **[server]**Initialize W_1 **for** each iteration r from 1 **to** R **do** **for** each party k **do** $\Delta W_r^k = \text{LocalUpdate}(k, W_r)$ **end for** $W_{r+1} = \frac{d_k}{D} \sum_k W_r^k$ **end for****[party [k]]****if** Round = 1 **then** $\bar{D}_k = \text{SMOTE-TOMEK}(D_k)$ Let x be the input and y the labels of the local data \bar{D}

Normalise local inputs

end if $W_r^k = \text{LocalUpdate}(k, W_k, \bar{D}_k)$ Send W_r^k to serverSMOTE-TOMEK(D):**for** $d_i, d_j \in D \cap C_l \mid d_j \in \text{Neighbours}(d_i)$ and $C_l \in M(D) = \text{Minority classes of } D$ **do** $\bar{d}_{i,j,r} = rd_i + (1-r)d_j$ with $r \in (0, 1)$ **end for** $S = \cup_{i,j,r} \bar{d}_{i,j,r}$ $\bar{D} = D \cup S$ $T = \{d_i \in \bar{D} \cap \hat{M}(\bar{D}) \mid d_i \in \text{Neighbours}(d_j) \forall d_j \in M(\bar{D})\}$ with $\hat{M}(\bar{D}) = \text{Majority classes of } \bar{D}$ $\bar{D} = \bar{D} \setminus T$ **return** \bar{D} LocalUpdate(k, W_r, \bar{D}_k):**for** each epoch from 1 **to** E **do** Train MLP using \bar{D}_k Compute prediction $\hat{y}_k = \text{MLP}(x_k)$ Calculate new weights using Fed+ ($Z^k = W_r$): $W_{r+1}^k = \theta[W_r^k - \nu \nabla f_k(W_r^k)] + (1-\theta)W_r$ **end for****return** W_{r+1}^k

where $c = \sum_{k=1}^K C_{kk}$ the total number of elements correctly predicted, $s = \sum_{i=1}^K \sum_{j=1}^K C_{ij}$ the total number of elements, $p_k = \sum_{i=1}^K C_{ki}$ the number of times that class k was predicted (column total), and $t_k = \sum_{i=1}^K i k$ the number of times that class k truly occurred (row total). In the multi-class case, MCC depends on correctly classified elements, because the total number of elements correctly predicted are multiplied by the total number of elements at the numerator and the weight of this product grows faster than the sum $\sum_{k=1}^K p_k \times t_k$. The denominator is used for rescaling the fraction to $[-1, 1]$.

Therefore, unlike accuracy and f1-score, MCC is affected by the classifier's performance to make correct predictions on all classes, independently of their ratios in the overall dataset. Indeed, accuracy and f1-score could produce misleading results when they are applied to unbalanced settings, which are commonly found in FL.

5.1.2. Cohen Kappa Score

Cohen Kappa Score (CKS) value is comprised between -1 and 1 , and it is also used to measure the reliability of the classifier's predictions. Practically, CKS takes into account the possibility of agreeing by chance, and measures the number of predictions it makes that cannot be explained by a random guess. CKS is defined by the formula:

$$CKS = \frac{a - p_c}{1 - p_c} \quad (8)$$

where a is the accuracy of the model, and p_c is the probability of get it right by chance. In order to calculate this p_c we have to take the confusion matrix. Let be p the multiplication of the total sum of the elements of a column divided by the total number of

Table 1
Metrics of the different scenarios using FedAvg and Fed+.

	Original		Balanced	
	FedAvg	Fed+	FedAvg	Fed+
Accuracy	0.844	0.888	0.893	0.928
F1-Score	0.814	0.87	0.888	0.925
MCC	0.64	0.738	0.874	0.913
CKS	0.607	0.72	0.87	0.912

elements, and the total sum of the elements of a row divided by the total number of elements. Then, p_c is the sum of the previous p applied to each column.

Let be C the confusion matrix, and K the number of classes, the multiclass formula would be:

$$CKS = \frac{c \times s - \sum_k p_k \times t_k}{s^2 - \sum_k p_k \times t_k} \quad (9)$$

where c , k , p_k , and t_k are the same as in (7).

In summary, CKS tries to correct the evaluation bias by taking into account the correct classification by a random guess, which in cases where there is unbalanced data, this probability of getting it right by chance is higher, which would lead CKS close to 0.

5.2. Results

In this section, we evaluate different scenarios considering the use of SMOTE-Tomek and FedAvg/Fed+ as aggregation techniques. Furthermore, we evaluate the impact of using a subset of the VeReMi vehicles's data to create a model that is shared with the other nodes. It should be noted that all results were obtained by running each scenario through 20 training rounds and 5 epochs each round. Furthermore, when Fed+ is used, θ is set as 0.98.

5.2.1. Different balancing settings and aggregation functions

For the evaluation of our approach using SMOTE-Tomek, and FedAvg/Fed+ as aggregation functions, we consider four scenarios: (1) Original VeReMi and FedAvg, (2) Original VeReMi and Fed+, (3) Balanced VeReMi with SMOTE-Tomek and FedAvg, and (4) Balanced VeReMi with SMOTE-Tomek and Fed+.

Fig. 4 shows a comparison among these scenarios considering the accuracy, f1-score, as well as the MCC and CKS values. Additionally, in Table 1 we summarize the results of the different metrics using FedAvg and Fed+. Specifically, Fig. 4(a) corresponds to the accuracy, f1-score, MCC, and CKS with the original VeReMi dataset. It shows that the value of these metrics is higher when using Fed+ compared to FedAvg. However, MCC (0.64 and 0.738 for FedAvg and Fed+, respectively) and CKS (0.607 and 0.72) values are quite lower compared to the accuracy for both aggregation functions (0.844 and 0.888), and f1-score (0.814 and 0.87). Therefore, it means that accuracy and f1-score of these scenarios (with an unbalanced dataset) do not provide a reliable perspective about the model's behavior. On the contrary, in the case of using the balanced version of VeReMi by using SMOTE-Tomek, Fig. 4(b), the corresponding values of MCC (0.874 and 0.913 for FedAvg and Fed+, respectively) and CKS (0.87 and 0.912) are much closer to accuracy (0.893 and 0.928) and f1-score (0.888 and 0.925), and therefore, these metrics can be considered as more reliable compared to the previous case. Furthermore, like in the unbalanced case, the use of Fed+ provides better results compared to FedAvg. Moreover, once the federated training is complete, the time needed to detect a certain attack (i.e., the delay during testing phase) is 0.7 ms on average.

We also compare these scenarios with the *distributed* case, where clients only train their own model independently with their data; that is, they do not share any information derived from their local training with other nodes. In this case, it should be noted that the accuracy of each node is adapted to its individual data, while in the federated scenarios, clients are affected by the local training of the other nodes. Therefore, to make the comparison as fair as possible, we use the dataset balanced through SMOTE-Tomek. Furthermore, as our federated scenarios are trained by using 20 rounds a 5 epochs each round, we consider 100 epochs for the distributed case (as the concept of round is not applicable in this case). With these parameters, the distributed case provides an accuracy value (0.887), which is lower than the federated scenario 4 (0.928). Indeed, the distributed case only provides better results compared to scenario 1, which provides an accuracy of 0.844. This means that the vehicles are able to classify better the traffic when sharing their knowledge through the federated scenarios.

Moreover, Fig. 5 shows the evolution of accuracy (or recall) and precision of every class in the VeReMi dataset considering scenario 4. Indeed, as the TN cannot be calculated in the multiclass case, only recall (that can be considered accuracy in this case), precision and f1-score can be provided. We associate class 0 to benign attack, and the classes 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 are the ones described in Section 4.1. Based on our results, we compare our work to [8] in Table 2. Furthermore, we also provide the accuracy (0.801) and precision (0.877) for class 0 that are not shown in the mentioned work. As shown, our solution offers better results considering the average value of accuracy and precision for almost any specific class in the dataset. It should be noted that, unlike [8], our evaluation is not based on an artificial division of the VeReMi dataset; instead, each vehicle in the dataset is considered as a FL client training with its own data.

(a) Metrics using the original Veremi dataset with FedAvg (Scenario 1) and Fed+ (Scenario 2)

(b) Metrics using the balanced Veremi dataset with FedAvg (Scenario 3) and Fed+ (Scenario 4)

Fig. 4. Comparison of the different scenarios with the original Veremi dataset and balanced Veremi through SMOTE-Tomek.

Table 2

Comparison of precision for each attack class in the Veremi dataset between our work and [8].

	Accuracy				
[8]	0.81	0.63	0.61	0.63	0.73
Our work	0.98	0.98	0.96	0.86	0.89
	Precision				
[8]	0.9455	0.6758	0.8675	0.8674	0.9294
Our work	0.983	0.946	0.983	0.834	0.887
	Class 1	Class 2	Class 3	Class 4	Class 5

(a) Accuracy

(b) Precision

Fig. 5. Accuracy and precision for each class in the Veremi dataset considering scenario 4.

5.2.2. Performance according to node selection

As described by [38], the use of a high number of clients for the federated training process could speed up the convergence of the global model and enhance its performance. However, this aspect is demonstrated in the case of a FL scenario with identically distributed data. Unlike such work, our proposal does not split the dataset in an artificial way, but each vehicle is considered as a FL client training over its local data. In our case, considering the scenario 4 as the baseline, we order the 449 clients by its number of samples, ranging from 62974 to 100 samples. Based on this, our premise is that there will be a certain number of clients where the model will converge, and adding more clients will not enhance the performance as the sizes are smaller every time. Fig. 6(a) shows the evolution of the accuracy by increasing the number of clients. As shown, the accuracy remains stable with more than 50 clients. However, reducing the number of clients leads to a decrease in the delay required for the training process, as shown in Fig. 6(b). The running time grows almost linearly with the addition of clients. In particular, the scenario with 50 vehicles takes 2573 s, and the training of the other cars takes 6572 s. So the total time is 9145 s, which means the delay is reduced compared to the case with 449 vehicles (9971 s). Thus, a potential user of the system can understand how much faster a decision on misbehavior

Fig. 6. Accuracy and time depending on the number of clients in the federated environment.

Table 3

All metrics when using 50 and 449 vehicles.

	50 vehicles	449 vehicles
Accuracy	0.929	0.928
Precision	0.929	0.931
Recall	0.927	0.926
F1-Score	0.926	0.926
FPR	0.014	0.014
MCC	0.913	0.913
CKS	0.912	0.912

can be obtained when using fewer vehicles for training the model in comparison with the accuracy reduction and therefore make an informed decision according to their resources and requirements.

Furthermore, we provide a comparison of both scenarios considering the federated models created with 50 and 449 vehicles in Table 3, which shows the different the values for the different metrics (including the False Positive Rate (FPR)) for both cases. As shown, the performance of both models is really similar, so that reducing the number of vehicles does not impact in the model being trained.

6. Conclusions and future work

In this work, we proposed an FL-enabled collaborative approach for misbehavior detection in the vehicular ecosystem. Our evaluation analyzed the impact of different balancing configurations of the dataset as well as different aggregation functions and number of FL clients by using the well-known VeReMi dataset. The results showed that the use of a balanced version of VeReMi through SMOTE-Tomek and Fed+ as an aggregation function improves the performance of the FL setting compared to existing literature. Furthermore, our approach is evaluated by using the division of data in such a dataset, where vehicles are directly considered as FL clients, which train over their local data. Moreover, we showed that the use of a subset of FL clients provides similar results while the latency in the training process is significantly reduced. As part of our future work in this area, we aim to explore the real-world application of FL in vehicular networks, including the practical challenges and potential solutions. We plan to use a federated version of an unsupervised approach based on autoencoders to address scenarios where vehicles do not have labeled data, and the evaluation of our solution using intermediate nodes to perform partial aggregations at the network edge. Additionally, we foresee the innovative use of roadside components as FL aggregators, which could ease federated training processes in vehicular networks. Indeed, this study paves the way for significant advancements in vehicular security, reinforcing the crucial role of FL in enhancing robust and reliable misbehavior detection in vehicular ecosystems.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Enrique Mármol Campos: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Resources, Validation, Visualization. **José L. Hernandez-Ramos:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Supervision, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Aurora González Vidal:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Software, Supervision, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Gianmarco Baldini:** Investigation, Methodology, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Antonio Skarmeta:** Funding acquisition, Project administration, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The data is shared through a link in the paper.

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